

Development of a Robust Onboard Data Processing Unit Using Commercial Off-the-Shelf System-on-Chips and Neuromorphic Co-Processors

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A paradigm shift for onboard processing in space is currently underway. In the coming years, we will demand more autonomy and flexibility from our satellites. Companies and institutions are exploring novel technologies, such as neuromorphic computing architectures and commercial-of-the-shelf (COTS) options, to cope with that demand. The following paper discusses the ongoing development of a data processing unit (DPU) that combines high-performance System-on-Chips (SoC), such as the NVIDIA Jetson Orin, with neuromorphic Network-on-Chip (NoC) co-processors, such as the BrainChip AKD1000 and AKD1500 or the SpiNNcloud Systems SpiNNaker2. The heterogeneous DPU will withstand harsh space environments through system-level hardening. It will function as a robust, reliable and user-friendly payload processing unit. Its successful integration onboard satellites will unlock a whole new level of potential for onboard algorithms.

1 Introduction

The demand for artificial intelligence (AI) in space applications is surging. However, the limited computational resources and power budget of existing spacecraft hardware still present significant challenges and hinder the adoption of onboard AI-based processing [1]. Our previous work proposed a novel data processing unit (DPU) architecture to address these issues [2]. The DPU combines various processing units in a heterogeneous envelope, leveraging and combining the benefits of different computing technologies. It incorporates technologies such as a System-on-Chip (SoC) with a CPU, GPU, and TPU with shared memory for high-performance AI processing and neuromorphic computing for ultra-low power and latency processing. Building upon this concept, we discuss our current development efforts, focusing on integrating an NVIDIA Jetson Orin NX SoC with neuromorphic co-processors such as a BrainChip AKD1000 or

SpiNNcloud Systems SpiNNaker2 into a reliable, robust, and user-friendly onboard computer. The DPU aims to drastically push the boundary of what we can expect of onboard processing capabilities in class-IV and class-V satellites in Low Earth Orbit (LEO) conditions. This paper briefly overviews the proposed architecture before delving into different system-level hardening techniques.

2 Architecture

The DPU's heterogeneous design combines a von Neumann and non-von Neumann computing architecture into one integrated system, as illustrated in Figure 1. It consists of two boards, *CORE* and *NEURON*, which can operate in unison or independently. *CORE* contains a high-performance System-on-Chip (SoC) for traditional processing, delivering top-notch edge performance for both AI and non-AI workloads. On the other hand, *NEURON* contains a Network-on-Chip (NoC) for neuromorphic processing, supporting cutting-edge energy-efficient algorithms, such as Spiking Neural Networks (SNN). Both boards are foreseen to interface with either sensors or the payload and can communicate with each other over a high-speed stacking bus. This flexibility allows the DPU to dynamically accommodate different processing modes, balancing heavy-duty and ultra-low-power processing.

2.1 High-Performance System-on-Chip

A Commercial-of-the-Shelf (COTS) SoC is central to *CORE*'s architecture, bringing CPU, GPU, and TPU (Deep Learning Accelerators) computing capabilities to the edge. Embedded GPUs, which have drastically improved in performance per watt over the years, could deliver the needed computational power for various space applications. The GPU4S study conducted

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Figure 1: Heterogeneous DPU Design: CORE (left), NEURON (right)

by the European Space Agency (ESA) in collaboration with Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC) concluded that the NVIDIA Embedded GPUs score higher on performance benchmarks than European alternatives [3]. On top of that, they have a tighter control over both software and hardware compared to other manufacturers, such as AMD. In addition, as seen in the most recent OBPMark benchmarking, the latest instalment in the NVIDIA Jetson series, the Orin, positions itself as one of the powerhouses of edge processing [4]. Some key features of the Jetson Orin (NX):

- **Processing:** The Orin NX integrates an 8-core ARM Cortex-A78AE CPU, a powerful integrated Ampere GPU with 1024 CUDA Cores, two NVDLA 2.0 AI Inferencing cores optimised for deep learning tasks and a Programmable Vision Accelerator (PVA) for computer vision workloads.
- **Safety:** The Orin NX includes ARM Reliability, Availability, and Serviceability (RAS) features for error tracking and correction. These protocols also enable the identification of the source of single-event effects (SEEs) caused by radiation.
- **Environmental:** The Orin NX is designed to withstand harsh thermal and mechanical conditions, ensuring reliable operation in space environments.
- **Configuration:** The Orin NX supports completely configurable power modes that can optimise power consumption based on mission requirements, which are crucial for managing limited satellite power budgets

2.1.1 Suitability for Space

The Orin’s predecessors, such as the Jetson TX2 and Jetson Xavier, had already undergone radiation testing. The Xavier showed a significant susceptibility to single-event effects (SEEs) in its caches; radiation testing with the help of the RAS features identified

that the cache tags were the leading source of single-event functional interrupts (SEFI) [5]. The Orin Series addresses these issues by switching to the Cortex-A78AE as CPU, hereby adding error correction codes (ECC), such as 1-bit correction and 2-bit detection error codes, in its caches. Recent proton irradiation tests confirmed the Orin NX’s robustness, demonstrating a drastically reduced SEFI and SEU cross-section compared to the Jetson Xavier [6]. The study further analysed various components of the Orin NX System-on-Module (SoM), including the DRAM, Ethernet PHY, and power delivery systems. Notable is that no definitive single-event latch-up (SEL) events were observed during the high-energy proton tests. The study concluded that the improvements between jetson generations make the NVIDIA Orin NX a robust and reliable choice for space applications, ensuring high performance and resilience in harsh environmental conditions.

2.2 Neuromorphic Network-on-Chip

A novel NoC is central to *NEURON*’s architecture, enabling neuromorphic computing capabilities within the spacecraft. This extends the concept of a heterogeneous stack-up to entirely new types of computing paradigms. Neuromorphic hardware can accelerate a broad portfolio of algorithms, ranging from machine learning to constrained optimisation and signal processing [7]. These algorithms are often associated with Spiking Neural Networks (SNN), an event-driven programming paradigm for neuromorphic hardware.

Since neuromorphic computing is yet to be a mature technology, few neuromorphic chips are available for purchase. On top of that, various chips follow different design approaches and are optimised for different algorithms, so the umbrella term "neuromorphic hardware" can be pretty ambiguous. For instance, the BrainChip AKD1000 or 1500 can accelerate traditional Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) in a sparse event-driven manner, achieving competitive AI inference in a sub-1W range. On the other hand of the spectrum, the SpiNNaker2 from SpiNNcloud, a spin-off from TU Dresden, can be programmed to execute arbitrary networks and neuron models. This flexibility facilitates use cases like constrained optimisation solving and scheduling. Nonetheless, all these chips follow similar, bio-inspired design principles, such as:

- **Fine-Grained Distributed Parallelism:** The AKD1000 has 80 Neural Processor Units (NPU), each with eight Neural Processing Engines (NPE), communicating over a Network-on-Chip (NoC). The SpiNNaker2 has 152 programmable ARM Cortex-M4 Cores as Processing Engines (PE) on a

NoC.

- **Co-Located Memory and Processing:** The AKD1000 has 100kB of local Static Random-Access Memory (SRAM) in every NPU for CNN weight storage. The SpiNNaker2 has 128kB SRAM in each core, which stores the precompiled program.
- **Event-Driven Compute Dynamics:** Each NPU in the AKD1000 computes only when triggered by an event, leveraging sparsity for increased energy efficiency. The SpiNNaker2 uses Dynamic Voltage and Frequency Scaling (DVFS) per core to increase global efficiency based on sparsity.

Other features often seen in neuromorphic chip designs are asynchronous or clockless designs, scalable-by-design strategies, and extreme energy-efficient architectures (albeit analogue or digital).

2.2.1 Suitability for Space

To our knowledge, no efforts are underway to characterise COTS neuromorphic chips for the space environment. Even the chips that have been to space, such as the Intel Loihi and the BrainChip AKD1000, have yet to be extensively tested on the ground. Some platforms, such as the AKD1500 and SpiNNaker2, are taped out in GlobalFoundries' 22nm FD-SOI process, which is naturally latch-up immune. An appropriate technology node and the correct utilisation of error correction mechanisms in the memory indicate that the chip might be more suited for space. We must conduct further radiation and environmental testing to understand better how these devices behave in space. Although radiation hardening of some neuromorphic IPs is an ongoing effort, we firmly believe that a COTS approach remains needed for lower-class missions. The NeuroSatCom study highlighted the potential self-healing capabilities of NoC-style neuromorphic processors [8]. Custom firmware could mitigate the failure of individual cores by distributing the workload to the other cores.

2.3 System-level Hardening

Different system-level hardening approaches must be considered since the onboard DPU proposed above mainly relies on COTS components. We use the concept of "safety barriers", both hardware and software, as explored in internal ESA working groups [9]. These safety barriers isolate the COTS components, both in hardware and software, from other mission-critical components, as well as limit error propagation and maintain availability. Such a barrier consists of typical

techniques used to guarantee the safety of COTS components in space systems, as described in this chapter. Inside the safety barrier, it is recommended to use COTS components that are at least automotive-grade. These components are designed to meet stringent reliability and safety standards, making them more suitable for harsh space conditions [9].

2.3.1 Supervisor

A supervisory system is an essential part of the safety barrier principle. This system plays a critical role in protecting the COTS components from Single Event Effects (SEE) and effects of Total Ionizing Dose (TID) failures. These COTS components can degrade or sustain permanent damage due to harsh space environments without adequate measures. A range of radiation hardening techniques can be implemented in the supervisory system to mitigate potential damage to the COTS components, thereby enhancing system reliability and robustness. We considered and evaluated several hardening techniques employed in published COTS-based designs, such as [10, 11]:

- Watchdogging
- Latch-up detection
- Temperature monitoring
- Power monitoring
- General protection measures
 - Power-On Reset (POR)
 - Overcurrent Protection (OCP)
 - Overvoltage Protection (OVP)
 - Undervoltage Protection (UVP)
 - Overtemperature Protection (OTP)
 - Undervoltage Lockout (UVLO)
- Built-in Redundancy
- Back-up Firmware
- Fallback Operating System

Any components providing the functionalities mentioned above should be radiation-tolerant/immune to protect the subsequent COTS parts. Hence, the destructive effects on those supervisor parts, such as Single-Event Latch-Ups (SEL) and Single-Event Burnouts (SEB), will be prevented, and Single-Event Transients (SETs) will be limited to known and manageable values [11].

In addition to protecting and monitoring the various components of the DPU through the implemented

housekeeping functionalities, the supervisor will control and recover, when necessary, the DPU by, for example, reloading configurations and changing power profiles. Additionally, the supervisory system logs all pertinent information into local memory, facilitating the investigation of any anomalies that may arise. A radiation-tolerant microcontroller (MCU) is proposed as a cost-effective, efficient, flexible, and reliable solution for monitoring, controlling, and communicating these functionalities. The software of that MCU should also be space-grade, such as a Real-Time Operating System (RTOS) or bare-metal code.

3 Results

This paper outlines the development of a data processing unit (DPU) that aims to improve onboard processing capabilities for space applications. The DPU will integrate high-performance System-on-Chips (SoCs) such as the NVIDIA Jetson Orin and neuromorphic Network-on-Chips (NoCs) like the BrainChip AKD1000/1500 or SpiNNcloud Systems SpiNNaker2 into a single platform. This combined system, which merges Von Neumann and non-Von Neumann computer architectures, will be capable of handling different computational loads within varying power envelopes. The design will use commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) components while implementing system-level hardening techniques to ensure reliability in challenging space environments.

4 Discussion

The integration of high-performance SoCs with neuromorphic NoCs poses some challenges due to the use of COTS components. With improved radiation characteristics over its predecessor, the NVIDIA Orin NX emerges as a strong candidate for AI-based processing tasks in space environments. Similarly, though still in the very premature stages of space qualification, neuromorphic processors offer promising avenues for energy-efficient, real-time processing of complex algorithms. System-level hardening techniques could effectively safeguard the DPU's functionality, ensuring that COTS components do not compromise the reliability required for space missions. Adopting a safety barrier system plays a pivotal role in maintaining system integrity. Future work will focus on extensive environmental testing of the neuromorphic coprocessors and the accompanying supervisory system to characterise the system as a whole.

5 Acknowledgements

The development is partly funded by the European Space Agency through the ARTES 4.0 Technology and Product Developments Activity programme with project name "Neuromorphic AI Onboard" and contract number 4000143001/23/UK/ND.

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